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**CASTIEL 2 – Coordination & Support
for National Competence Centres on a European Level Phase 2**

Project Number: 101102047

D5.3

First report on awareness, impact and outreach

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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Author(s):	Miriam Koch, Guntram Berti	USTUTT
Contributor(s):	WP5 Members	
Approved by	Project Management Team	18.12.2023
Reviewer	Cosima Weyers	USTUTT
Reviewer	Laura Morselli	CINECA
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List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
C2ISS	CASTIEL 2 Information Sharing System
CD	Corporate Design
CoE	Centre of Excellence
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
D	Deliverable
EBDVF	European Big Data Value Forum
GA	Grant Agreement
HPC	High-Performance Computing
ISC	ISC High Performance – wissenschaftliche Konferenz zu Supercomputing/HPC
JU	Joint Undertaking
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
NCC	National Competence Centre
PMT	Project Management Team
SC	The International Conference for High Performance Computing Networking, Storage, and Analysis (Supercomputing)
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

The document “D5.3 First report on awareness, impact and outreach” is the third deliverable of CASTIEL 2’s Work Package 5 (WP5): Awareness, Impact and Outreach. This document reports on the communication and dissemination activities from and related to CASTIEL2. It will be updated and reported on in D5.5 and D5.7 (M24 and M36).

WP5 plans and implements communication and dissemination measures that are related to and support the achievement of the CASTIEL 2 project’s objectives, as well as assisting the National Competence Centres (NCCs) of the EuroCC 2 project and EuroHPC JU funded Centres of Excellence (CoEs) in HPC with their communication efforts.

This deliverable 5.3 is divided into two main parts: the first covers the communication and dissemination work, the second presents the support of National Competence Centres for High Performance Computing (NCCs) and the Centres of Excellence (CoEs).

Main achievements in this phase were onboarding the CoEs and transferring the communication to phase two, new formats like the communication coffee break have started. The second phase of the project has been communicated on various channels, all KPIs are well under way.

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1 Introduction

The Coordination and Support Action (CSA) CASTIEL 2 leads to cross-European networking activities between National Competence Centres and EuroHPC JU funded Centres of Excellence in HPC-related topics. The other CoEs that were funded in previous funding programmes will be included in collaboration when beneficial. In the following, CoE refers to the CoEs funded by the EuroHPC JU, if not specified otherwise.

CASTIEL 2 focuses on four core areas: Competences, Training, Industry Collaboration as well as Communication and Dissemination.

WP5 in CASTIEL – Awareness, Impact and Outreach – operates on multiple levels. Firstly, this WP communicates the CASTIEL 2 projects’ contents, aims, and results. Secondly, this WP maintains the EuroCC and hpccoe brands. Thirdly, the support of NCCs and CoEs is also in the scope of work. (The creation and maintenance of the C2ISS and a newly developed CI/CD is also part of this work package, but since these topics have their own deliverables, they will not be described here.)

The main goals for this work have also been set in the initial dissemination strategy:

- *Continue and increase awareness about the EuroCC and hpccoe brands*
- *Create and promote the Competence and Excellence Network Brand*
- *Support the CoEs’ and NCCs’ communication efforts*

Figure 1: EuroCC and hpccoe main logos

The second goal foreseen in the initial strategy was to create an umbrella brand for the EuroCC and hpccoe brands. However, seen that updating and maintaining the hpccoe brand requires more effort than initially estimated and not to overburden the new CoEs with too much branding work, creating and implementing the umbrella brand is on hold for now. This leaves the two main goals:

- *Continue and increase awareness about the EuroCC and hpccoe brands*
- *Support the CoEs and NCCs communication efforts*

This report will give a comprehensive and extensive overview about the work done and the results achieved in these tasks during the project. Section 2 will summarise the efforts and results when it comes to dissemination and communication, Section 3 shows how the NCCs and CoEs are supported and Section 4 will provide a summary and outlook towards the next project months.

2 Dissemination and Communication

In this Section, the communications about and from the projects in year one are presented and the overall progress is evaluated.

2.1 Goals and Channels

The main goal of this WP's outreach efforts was to further establish the NCCs as first contact point to the "world of HPC" and the CoEs as excellence hubs in specific domains and associated with spearheading algorithm development (the stakeholders chosen in the initial strategy can be found in D5.1 Initial Dissemination Plan). A focus of CASTIEL 2 is to extend the brands outside of the HPC ecosystem.

The communication channels from CASTIEL 1 were kept (EuroCC ACCESS, X (former Twitter) and LinkedIn). The FocusCoE channels were reactivated and rebranded to the hpccoe brand. The main channels remain (as in phase 1 as proven effective) the web channels and events. To see the evaluation of how these channels contributed to the goals, see Table 1, the impact was estimated based on lead generation, brand awareness and reach with a scoring system.

Channel	Impact in Target Group
EuroCC ACCESS ⁱ	Mid
hpccoe.eu ⁱⁱ	Mid
X (Twitter) EuroCC ⁱⁱⁱ	Low
X (Twitter) hpccoe ^{iv}	Low
LinkedIn EuroCC ^v	High
LinkedIn hpccoe ^{vi}	High
Press Releases	Mid
Events	Very High

Table 1: Evaluation of Channels by CASTIEL

The table shows that the X (Twitter) channels have been rated as a low impact. This is because of the development of the platform in the last year. The HPC community is not as present as it used to be, since technical and content quality of the platform declined. This WP monitors current and future alternatives. Mastodon was considered, but given the low representation of the target group, not implemented. Once the alternative from Meta, Threads, will be available in the EU, it will presumably be a good candidate. Switching from X to Threads will need to be coordinated with the NCCs and CoEs.

2.1.1 Update on Event Participation

Table 2 shows a summary of events in which CASTIEL 2 participated, a description of how the project was represented and a short evaluation of their effectiveness.

Event	Date	Summary	Evaluation
EuroHPC Summit Week	20.03. – 23.03.2023	Participated in Conference Programme	Valuable for establishing the brands within the HPC ecosystem
ISC 2023	22.05. – 24.05.2023	Represented in EuroHPC JU Booth	Valuable for establishing the brands within the HPC ecosystem, some industry contact
Supercomputing Day Luxembourg	04.05.2023	Participated in Sessions & presented a high-level view of the CoEs & their codes	Valuable for establishing the brands within the HPC ecosystem
EBDVF 2023	25.10. – 27.10.2023	Participated with a booth, participated in Conference Programme	Valuable for reaching an industrial target group, industry contact
SC 2023	14.11. – 17.11.2023	Represented in HLRS Booth	Valuable for establishing the brands within the international HPC ecosystem

Table 2: Description and Evaluation of Events Visited

2.1.2 HPC Industry Summit in Berlin

On 18–19 October 2023, together with the FF4EuroHPC project, a joint event towards industry and state representatives was held – the HPC Industry Summit.

The conference consisted of two different parts: a project-internal one, exclusively for the WPLs of the NCCs, and an external one that was open to visitors and also livestreamed via YouTube. The first day focussed on introductory content such as overviews about HPC+ and its applications and featured Success Stories from the EuroCC project. The second day featured more in-depth topics and premiered Success Stories from the FF4EuroHPC project. See Figure 2 for details of the agenda.

Figure 2: Agenda of the HPC Industry Summit

For the communication of the conference, a visual identity has been created for the dissemination of the event (see Figure 3):

Figure 3: Visual Identity of EuroCC@Montenegro

The first feedback by the participants was very positive, explicitly praising the excellent networking opportunities and interesting talks and use cases. Requests for a second iteration of the event have already been received from SMEs and start-ups.

2.2 Content Generation from the NCCs/CoEs and Reach Multiplication

In phase 2 of the project, the NCCs and CoEs already have a great output of content themselves, so the focus shifted more from active content generation to reach multiplication. For that, the NCCs and CoEs have access to content plans for the social media channels (they can provide content and WP5 posts the content to the EuroCC/hpccoe channels) as well as their own content areas on the respective websites (editable themselves in case of EuroCC ACCESS, editable through WP5 upon request in case of hpccoe.eu). Through promoting these channels further, the reach benefit for the Centres grows. Furthermore, an increasing amount of cross-promoting can be seen, where NCCs and CoEs share each other's content, thus increasing reach again.

2.3 Update on EuroCC Brand

The EuroCC brand continues to be well received by the NCCs. While the main project logo was updated in phase two, the NCC logos remain the same to ensure brand continuity. In the first phase, there was a light and a dark version of the CD. In phase two, only the light one will be continued. The EuroCC brand (See D5.1 – Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan) is overall well accepted and implemented by the NCCs, with varying degrees of adhesiveness to the CD guidelines.

2.4 Update on hpccoe Brand

The hpccoe brand was reactivated by re-working and updating the hpccoe website as well as taking ownership of the Focus CoE channels which have been rebranded to the hpccoe brand. A brand handbook is being developed together with the CoEs to grant representation as an umbrella brand for the CoEs and will be implemented by the CoEs in year two.

2.5 Update on KPIs

For the KPIs set in the GA, the final status is given here in form of a table (see Table 3) including comments, if necessary. All KPIs are well under way.

Tool	KPI	Target (M36)	Status
Publications	Press Releases	2	1
	Success Story Booklets	2	0
Events	CASTIEL/Network of NCC/CoEs presentations at conferences/events	20	5
	Significant presence at events (e.g. booths)	5	2
	Number of own events (public)	3	1

Social Media	Number of Twitter postings, Followers	Daily postings, 300 Followers p.a.	Daily Postings, >185 new followers
	Number of LinkedIn Postings, Followers	Weekly Postings, 250 Followers p.a.	Weekly Postings, >360 new followers
Reference in external media channels (Online & Offline)	Press Clippings	40	10
Websites	Number of visits	10,000 unique p.a.	14.500

Table 3: KPIs and Update

3 Support of NCCs and CoEs

Another core task of WP5 is to support the communication teams in the NCCs and CoEs through a series of mechanisms. These mechanisms are described in section 3.3. Additionally, an update on the NCCs' communication efforts is given to create a comprehensive picture.

3.1 Summary of CoEs' Efforts

This WP collected communication reporting files regularly, including all relevant KPIs. In detail, these are reported in the Funding and Tenders portal of the respective CoE project. A summary can be found in Table 4.

KPI	# achieved by CoEs in total
Publications	63
Events organised	41
Events attended	95
Press Clippings	28
Press Releases	18
Twitter Followers	2557
LinkedIn Followers	1841

Unique Visitors on Webpages	114652
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Table 4: KPIs of CoEs - Summarised

3.2 Summary of NCCs Efforts

This WP collected communication reporting files regularly, including all relevant KPIs. In detail, these are reported in the Funding and Tenders portal for the EuroCC project. A summary can be found in Table 5:

KPI	# achieved by NCCs in total
Publications	2
Events organised	196
Events attended	397
Press Clippings	223
Press Releases	22
Twitter Followers	5363
LinkedIn Followers	6879
Unique Visitors on Webpages	233805

Table 5: KPIs of NCCs - Summarised

3.3 General Support and Coffee Breaks

In general, Communication Champions can always approach the WP with their request for assistance. In the first year of the project, this was mostly due to staff change in the existing or new staff in the new Centres, who were then onboarded individually by members of this WP. WP5 attended the “NCCs-CoEs online meeting” organised by CASTIEL2-WP2 to fully onboard the CoEs with CASTIEL 2 activities. The breakout room dedicated to WP5 during the meeting was an important chance to get to know and onboard the CoEs.

Furthermore, the concept of a communications coffee break was successfully launched. These topic-centred 45-minute sessions allow an informal exchange of experiences between the NCCs’ and CoEs’ Communication Champions. The format was received well and already resulted in further collaborations among the teams.

Finally, the concept of the catch-up sessions from phase 1 was modified and re-applied to the champions group. Instead of small group sessions, it will be held in one singular session at the

beginning of year two. There, the communication champions can give feedback and bundle requests for WP5.

3.4 Distributed Materials

In phase one, a plethora of material was produced and distributed to the NCCs (e.g. print templates, social media material etc.). These materials were updated (e.g. with new funding disclaimers and logos) and, when appropriate, also made available to the CoEs. It was also decided, which material should also be available to the CoEs, which is due to the different structures of the Centres. For example, templates produced for the NCCs will not be of use for the CoEs, since they have their own corporate design and do not use the EuroCC brand. Material like the imagepool filled with AI generated, royalty free imagery, or a list of all social media channels was made accessible to all.

3.5 Specific CoE Support

During the first year, the working group of the CoE Communication Champions was set up, as an additional forum to the general coffee break meetings to discuss and develop specific dissemination aspects of interest to the CoEs in particular. Meetings are anticipated in regular intervals every few months. One of the first decisions was to set up a social media content plan which serves initially Twitter and LinkedIn which are the most used channels of the CoEs. Starting after the summer break, the still existing channels from FocusCoE were revived as @HPCCoE (Twitter) and @HPC CoE (LinkedIn) and each week one of the new CoEs was presented. After these 10 weeks, a free content schedule is anticipated where CoEs fill in their upcoming events and news.

One of the areas of interest for many CoEs was identified as outreach to young people, students and young professionals. This topic will be followed up in the second year.

Regarding the hpccoe.eu web site, material was collected from the CoEs to update the web site which was also brought up-to-date.

Lastly, WP5 supported WP4 and WP2 with the organisation of the series of public “code of the month” events (see D4.1 and D2.1 for details) by promoting the webinars over mailing lists and social media of the CoEs and NCCs, and by posting the recordings on the EuroCC home page.

4 Conclusion and Outlook on CASTIEL 2

The work done by WP 5 was based on the initial strategy for communication and dissemination presented in D5.1. This strategy has been adapted in some minor aspects (e.g. postponing the umbrella brand), but mainly followed through. The significant communication KPIs from the NCCs and CoEs show a broad reach of the respective brands.

Since the staff changes in the NCCs are now mainly done and the new CoEs have established their structures, one of the main focus points for the next year is to continue work with the communication champions to further find out which formats, measures or tools could benefit their communication work best.

Furthermore, the collaboration with the other WPs of CASTIEL2 will be intensified to support them in their work that touches on communications. For example, WP4 will organise bundled participation in sectorial events, which of course will be strongly supported by this WP.

Overall, this WP assesses itself in a good progress when it comes to the reported tasks. The KPIs are well underway and the communication channels, both external and internal, are running well. This report is going to be updated in D5.5 “Second report on awareness, impact and outreach”, as well as D5.7 “Final report on awareness, impact and outreach”.

5 References

i <https://www.eurocc-access.eu/>

ii <https://www.hpccoe.eu/>

iii https://twitter.com/EuroCC_project

iv <https://twitter.com/HPCCoE>

v <https://www.linkedin.com/company/43366031>

vi <https://www.linkedin.com/company/43336867/>